

Pulatova L.U., Eshkaraev S.Ch.

Termiz university of economics and service, Termiz City, street of Faravon, 4B-house

e-mail: Pulatovalola04@gmail.com

Absract

“*Mediasia macrophylla Pimen*” is both a medicinal and spice plant and is popular with the people for its a number of healing properties. The ground top of the alga is a fragrant ingredient in perfumery, a powerful appetite suppressant in medicine. Algal contains substances that have the properties of treating rheumatism, nephritis, eczema, herpes, gastrointestinal, liver and damaged areas.

Keywords: *Mediasia macrophylla*, folk medicine, gives aroma, *Foeniculum vulgare*, nervous (E)-anethol, thymol, carvacrol, essential oil composition

Аннотация.

“*Mediasia macrophylla pimen*” является как лекарственным, так и пряным растением и широко известен своими целебными свойствами. Надземная часть альгора считается ароматизатором в парфюмерии, мощным аппетитным средством в медицине. Алгор содержит вещества, способные лечить ревматизм, нефрит, экзему, герпес, желудочно – кишечный тракт, печень и поврежденные участки.

Ключевые слова: *Mediasia macrophylla*, народная медицина, придает аромат, *Foeniculum vulgare*, нейрон (E)-анетол, тимол, карвакрол, композиция эфирных масел.

INTRODUCTION. *Mediasia* is a perennial plant in the family Apiaceae. The upper parts of the stems are up to 50-80 cm long, have leaves and inflorescences. The stems are rounded, sharply twisted, poorly pubescent, branching in the middle to a wide row. The leaves are thick, short on both sides along the veins, covered with fine hairs, the rhizome leaves are in short bands. The Leaf bands are rounded, with a gray Fine pubescence, the plate is oblong-triangular, divided into two double-pointed three pieces.

In folk medicine, the stem, leaves and flowers of the plant are used. The plant has a positive effect on the nervous system, improves the cardiovascular system, normalizes blood pressure. Unig ground top is used in the food industry, making canned meat and fish. Tea brewed from the leaves of khushtaam as a medicinal remedy raises the mood and refreshes the psyche. Added to meals will prevent rapid nausea.

Place of growth and distribution: grows on rocky slopes, in the middle region foothills of the mountains. It is found in Tashkent, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions. The raw materials of the algoroti plant should be harvested by the beginning period of flowering and fruiting in the cover.

https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fplanta-medica.uz%2Fmediasia-macrophylla-regel-et-schmalh-pimenov-mediaziya-krupnolistnaya%2F&psig=AOvVaw1OIh4DKNh0uT3y4IhNSmnl&ust=1729429297204000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBcQjhxqFwoTCMDJ8b_AmokDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAK

The Assembly must be carried out with a sickle or knife. The raw materials collected in this way are air-dried under the porch or in the shade on air-well-rotating chords, spread on paper or fabric in a thin layer and rolled often. According to TU 88,-13-7:2007, the moisture content should not exceed 13%, the total ash content, not more than 12.8%, the essential oil in absolutely dry raw materials should not be less than 0.3%. Sifted parts with holes with a diameter of 1 mm should not be less than 63.8 %.

The presence of a huge amount of essential oil and complex lipids in plant seeds, leaves and flowers makes it possible to use it as a source of fragrant ether in the food industry. Milk and dairy products with the addition of algae plant keep their composition natural for a long time. Its Leaf and seeds, dried in the shade, are used in salting vegetables. The fact that it retains its pleasant aroma for a long time is the main reason for the increased interest in this spice and medicinal plant.

✓ https://planta-medica.uz/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/mediasia_macrophylla-2.jpg

Table 1.

Biochemical composition of the Apiaceae family in the Samarkand region

Type of Plant organs Essential oils Coumarins Flavonoids Fatty oils (U ; I c O, t Steroids
Phenolcarbonic acids Carbohydrates Vitamins C

- 1) Galagania fragrantissima Supervision. part + + + - - - - -
- 2) Elwendia chaerophylloides is supervised. part +
- 3) E. persica Above.Part of the Fruit + + _ _ + _ - - - - -
- 4) Mediasia macrophylla Roots of Nadz.Part of the Fruit + + + +

Table 2.

Distribution of spicy - aromatic plants of the Apiaceae family in the Samarkand region.

- 1) Carum carvi L - Cumin ordinary Biennial + - + - -
- 2) Coriandrum sativum L.- Annual Coriander + + + - +
- 3) Echinophora sibthorpiana Guss. -Thornbill Siebthorpe Perennial + + + + +
- 4) Galagania fragrantissima Lipsky -Galagania fragrant Perennial + + + - -
- 5) Mediasia macrophylla (Regel & Schmalh) Pimenov - Mediasia large-leaved Perennial + + +

Thus, the spicy-aromatic plants of the **Apiaceae** family are distributed in 7 species, of which 5 species are perennials, 1 species is biennial and 1 species is annual.

Polyacetylenic glucosides (1–5) were isolated from the MeOH extract of Mediasia macrophylla. Their structures were established by spectroscopic analyses. Compounds 2–4 were the first examples of C10-polyacetylenic glucosides found in the family Umbelliferae, while compound 1 was a unique polyacetylenic glucoside possessing an α -pyrone moiety.

<https://ars.els-cdn.com/content/image/1-s2.0-S0031942209005433-fx1.jpg>

The preventative function of plants for a food was found during this study. It was observed that some plants can prevent meat and milk based foods from spoiling during hot seasons. The aerial part of Mediasia macrophylla is usually added to a milk or lactic product to keep it fresh (Fig. 2). This

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-10

addition gives products a good scent and taste in hot seasons. Boughs of *Juniperus seravshanica* and *Juniperus turkestanica* are used to cook the most popular food, known as Archa kabob (Fig. 3). It is mutton, prepared in a special oven called a tandoor (Tandir – Uzbek name). The heat from a tandoor was traditionally generated by a charcoal or wood fire, burning within the tandoor itself, thus exposing the food to live fire, radiant heat cooking, and hot-air, convection cooking, and smoking by the fat and food juices that drip on to the charcoal. Temperatures in a tandoor can approach 480°C, and it is common for tandoor ovens to remain lit for long periods of time to maintain a high cooking temperature. *Juniperus seravshanica* and *J. turkestanica* make food smell appetizing and taste much more delicious. Furthermore, it allows the dish to be kept approximately for 1 month, which is very convenient in field conditions.

<https://ars.els-cdn.com/content/image/1-s2.0-S2352618115000062-gr2.jpg>

Mediasia macrophilla is usually added to a milk or lactic product to keep it fresh.

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fm.olx.uz%2Fd%2Fobyavlenie%2Ftandir-gusht->

Conclusion: In folk medicine, a tincture-shaped algot earthen top is used as a herb driver and invigorating agent in the treatment of liver diseases, and is also used as a spice and invigorating agent.

References:

1. English: 1. O.K.KHOJIMATOV, H.Q. HAYDAROV, D.T. KHAMRAEVA, D.A.Imamova, A.N.KHUJANOV. Atlas of Medicinal Plants of Uzbekistan.
2. Умурзакова З.И., Мукумов И.У. Род *Elwendia* Kashkadarya region // Kharzm Mamnun Academy newsletter . Khiva , 2022, 9/1, стр. 130 – 135.
3. Мукумов И.У., Хасанов М.А. Distribution of the Apiaceae Lindl family in the flora of the Turkestan range / Kharzm Mamnun Academy newsletter Khiva, 2022, 4/1. Стр. 58 – 61
4. Ilkhom Uktamovich Mukumov, Murtoza Abdivalievich Hasanov, Yulduzoy Erkin kizi Ikromova, Tolibjon Mukimov. Distribution and Chemical Composition of Monocarpic Plants of the Apiaceae Family in Tien Shan Mountain. // American Journal of Plant sciences. Vol.13, 2, February 2022, pp. 265 - 276.
5. Muqimov I.U. *Ferula L.* - sources of bioactive compounds Tashkent, 1993, 18 c.
6. Muqimov I.U. Distribution and chemical composition of algebraic plants belonging to the celery family in the Jizzakh region. Food security: national and global challenges. Scientific journal. Samarkand, 2022, № 1, c.61 - 64.
7. Muqimov I.U. Distribution and chemical composition of algebraic plants belonging to the celery family in the Jizzakh region. Food security: national and global challenges. Scientific journal. Samarkand, 2022, 14-15 october, 181 - 183 pages.

